

Tourniquet Study Informed Consent Form

Study Title: “A Transparent Elasticized Adhesive Occlusive Compression Bandage for Use as an Arterial Tourniquet.”

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Co-Principal Investigator: Dr. Joseph Ambrose 330 707-0771 Jambrose52@gmail.com

Institutional Review Board (IRB): Chairperson of the Mercy Health Youngstown IRB, Dr. Timothy Barreiro at 330-480-3610

Study Site: 540 Parmalee Avenue Suite 410, Youngstown, OH 44510

What is the purpose of this research?

The purpose of this research is to test the safety and efficacy of an elastic tape for use as an emergency tourniquet. Efficacy will be determined by the presence or absence of blood flow measured after a tourniquet is applied. The relative safety of one tourniquet to another will be determined by comparing the pressure measured between each tourniquet and the skin. A lower pressure is considered safer relative to a higher pressure. The elastic tape is the investigational device. The elastic tape is manufactured by [ENTROTECH, INC.](#) at 1245 KINNEAR ROAD, COLUMBUS, OH 43212. The tape is similar to an existing product called Battle Wrap. A 2 inch wide version and a 4 inch wide version of the elastic tape will be used in this study.

Who is this form for?

This Informed Consent Form is for healthy adult men and women between 18 and 55 years of age who have an upper thigh circumference larger than 24 inches and wish to volunteer for a research study involving emergency tourniquets.

You are being asked to be in a research study that will involve twenty five (25) human subjects. Research studies include only people who volunteer to participate. This consent form explains your rights and includes details about the study such as its purpose, duration, required procedures, alternative treatments and key contacts. The risks and potential benefits are also explained. You may withdraw from the study at any time. Carefully read this document, and take time to discuss it with family, friends and the study team. Please ask the study team any questions you may have. If you have questions later, or would like additional information, you can contact Marcus Migura at (619) 436-7323, Migura@cryptoheaven.com or Dr. Joseph Ambrose at (330) 707-0771, Jambrose52@gmail.com. In the event of research related injury you should contact Dr. Joseph Ambrose. If you have any questions regarding your rights as a research subject, you should contact the Chairperson of the Mercy Health Youngstown IRB (Institutional Review Board), Dr. Barreiro at (330) 480-3610.

If you decide you want to be in this study, you will need to sign and date this consent form. You will receive a copy of this consent form for your personal records so you can refer to it while you are in this study.

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How long will I be in the study?

For this research you will visit the study site one time. The study site address is 540 Parmalee Avenue Suite 410, Youngstown, OH 44510, there is a map provided at the end of this document. This one visit will require approximately two consecutive hours of your time. Marcus Migura will contact you to complete scheduling as needed.

What is a tourniquet?

A tourniquet is a strap or band that is wrapped around an arm or leg until it is tight enough to compress the underlying blood vessels, and thereby stop blood from flowing past the tourniquet. An inflatable blood pressure cuff is an example of a tourniquet. When measure blood pressure is measured, the cuff compresses the underlying blood vessels and stops blood flow, but it only stops blood flow for about 10-15 seconds. When a tourniquet is used in emergency situations, the tourniquet is used to stop blood flow for as long as is necessary.

Why are tourniquets used?

There are two setting where tourniquets are commonly used. In the controlled surgical setting, like a planned surgery to repair an injury to the arm or leg, which often require a tourniquet to be used for more than an hour. The second setting is the combat setting, where emergency tourniquets are commonly used to stop potentially life threatening bleeding from an arm or leg by stopping the flow of blood to the arm or leg. In this situation the tourniquet is left on for as long as necessary.

Why is this research needed?

Information is needed before an informed decision regarding the use of tourniquets can be made. While published information clearly indicates that the correct use of tourniquets can save lives, there is little information about the limitations of a specific tourniquet design or about techniques for applying tourniquets. One reason for this is the fact that the FDA does not required new tourniquets to provide evidence of safety or effectiveness before they are sold to the public. As a result, there little information available to determine if a new tourniquet should be effective before a patient's life depends upon it. The military considers tourniquet use a priority because the majority of preventable combat deaths are caused by massive bleeding from an arm or leg. The information gained in this research could inform decisions aimed at eliminating preventable combat deaths.

How can you test a tourniquet on healthy volunteers?

Fortunately, it is possible to test if an emergency tourniquet should be effective without testing it on a person injured in combat. Ultrasound will be used to see if blood is flowing through major blood vessels beyond a tourniquet. If a tourniquet is effective, the pulsing flow of blood should stop as it is tightened. With the use of ultrasound and healthy uninjured volunteers, the tourniquet efficacy can be tested in a controlled laboratory setting.

What happens when I show up for the visit?

Your enrollment information and consent form will be verified before you are assigned a letter identifier that will be used in place of your name for the collection of study data. We estimate that two consecutive hours will be required to complete the study procedures. The first hour will be used to collect vital signs and baseline measurements. You will be asked to change into scrub bottoms before procedures begin. Vital signs and baseline measurements will include age, gender, body height, body weight, waist circumference, upper thigh circumference, middle thigh circumference, lower thigh circumference, knee height, thigh length, body temperature, heart rate, blood oxygen saturation, blood pressure measured in both upper arms, and blood pressure measured in both lower legs.

The second hour will be used for tourniquet testing. You will be seated at the edge of the exam table with your leg be extended to another support. Ultrasound will be used to record baseline measurement of the major blood vessel behind the knee, below where the tourniquets will be placed on the thigh.

This picture is provided to show how your leg will be positioned for tourniquet application.

- Ultrasound blood flow sensor is shown circled in red, below #1.
- **Note:** There is no pressure sensor shown in this photograph.

Tactilus is a stretchable pressure sensor (similar to spandex cloth) and will be place on top of the scrubs and wrapped around the thigh. The scrubs pant leg can be folded up over the sensor or another thin drape added on top. Then the tourniquet will be applied and tightened while ultrasound is used to monitor blood flow in the blood vessel behind your knee. If the blood flow stops for one minute then the tourniquet will be considered successful and the tourniquet will be removed. The pressure below the tourniquet will be recorded as the final tourniquet pressure.

The procedure can then be repeated with the next tourniquet on the opposite thigh. The first tourniquet will be applied to the left thigh, the second tourniquet to the right thigh, the third tourniquet to the left thigh, and the fourth tourniquet to the right thigh. There are four (4) different tourniquet devices that will be tested. Each volunteer will have each tourniquet applied once. The sequence in which the different tourniquets are applied has been randomly assigned by a computer program.

The tourniquet pressure that will be required to stop blood flow is dependent upon the thigh circumference and the effective tourniquet width. The pressure of the tourniquet will be monitored to prevent excessive pressures. If there is still blood flow at 475 mmHg then the tourniquet will be considered ineffective.

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What tourniquets will be used in this research?

Special Operations Forces Tactical Tourniquet-Wide (SOFTT-W) by TACTICAL MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, INC. 1250 Harris Bridge Road, Anderson, SC 29621.

The SOFTT-W is a 1.5 inch wide windlass type tourniquet in common use by the US military and is recommended by National Association of Emergency Medical Technicians (NAEMT) guidelines. The pressure under the tourniquet will be monitored with the Tactilus pressure monitoring system during application, and if the pressure reaches 350 mmHg without stopping blood flow then a second tourniquet will be added just above the first. The combined width is now three inches, and the surface area doubled. Two tourniquets side by side are expected to stop blood flow at a lower pressure than a single tourniquet alone. Current NAEMT guidelines recommend adding a second tourniquet if one is not effective. This study has self-imposed the 350 mmHg threshold because the NAEMT guidelines are intended for actual casualties, and the upper limit for tightness is not defined because there is no way to measure the pressure when in normal use. The SOFTT-W or a comparable

windlass tourniquet has been routinely applied to healthy soldiers during tourniquet training so that they understand what it will be like. The most common complaint is pain caused by pinching.

Automatic Tourniquet System (ATS) 1500 by Zimmer, INC. formerly ASPEN LABORATORIES, INC. P.O. Box 3936, Englewood, CO 80155 -3936

The ATS is a 4.0 inch wide inflatable cuff tourniquet with internal sensors to determine when blood flow has been stopped. This pneumatic tourniquet is representative of a tourniquet commonly used in the controlled surgical setting.

The Automatic Tourniquet System (ATS) is a 4 inch wide pneumatic type tourniquet, very similar to a blood pressure cuff. The most significant difference is the duration. In this study each tourniquet is intended to stop the blood flow for 1 minute, while a blood pressure cuff would be approximately 10-15 seconds.

**Battle Wrap (The Investigational or Experimental Device) by
Entrotech Inc. 1245 KINNEAR ROAD, COLUMBUS, OH 43212.**

Entrotech manufactures a device called Battle Wrap that is registered with the FDA. Battle Wrap is cleared for marketing and is intended to be used as an elastic bandage. Battle Wrap is not cleared or approved for the intended use under investigation (for use as a tourniquet). The investigational device has been created by modifying Battle Wrap for use as a tourniquet. The investigational device is a highly elastic adhesive tape manufactured by Entrotech Inc. This study will test both a 2 inch width and a 4 inch width version of the Battle Wrap tourniquet tape. The Battle Wrap tourniquet tape is the “investigational device” which means it is the “experimental device.”

(Above) 2 inch wide
tape

(Left) 4 inch wide tape

(Above) Simulated use of Battle Wrap as an elastic
bandage.

The Battle Wrap tourniquet tape is an example of an elastic type tourniquet. This will be the first test of Battle Wrap for use as a tourniquet. While there is no previous documented experience with the Battle Wrap tourniquet tape, the design of Battle Wrap is substantially similar to the Esmarch bandage, also known as Esmarch tourniquet. Use of the Esmarch Bandage began in 1866, and in the last ten years it has been re-introduced to battlefield medicine under the new name Stretch Wrap and Tuck Tourniquet (SWAT-T). The SWAT-T is a 4-6 inch wide latex free synthetic rubber bandage, essentially a big rubber band that is stretched as it is wrapped around the thigh. The Battle Wrap tourniquet tape functions in the same way but it is made of plastic and has an adhesive side which helps it stay tight, and keeps it from loosening if handled roughly.

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What are the possible risks?

There are some risks associated with this study that you need to be aware of. The following things might happen to you in this study:

- Pain at or below the tourniquet
- Blisters at the tourniquet site
- Abrasions at the tourniquet site
- Contusions at the tourniquet site
- Pinching at the tourniquet site
- Numbness at or below the tourniquet
- Tingling at or below the tourniquet
- Other altered sensations at or below the tourniquet

If you experience any effects that are not listed here should be reported to Dr. Joseph Ambrose at (330) 707-0771, Jambrose52@gmail.com.

It is important for you remember that this study involves research with an investigational tourniquet which may expose you to currently unforeseeable risks.

Note: Pregnant women may not participate in this research study.

If your continued participation could expose you or another person to unacceptable risk then your participation may be terminated without your consent.

The methods used in this study are similar to the methods used by three military studies to test tourniquets. In these three studies no adverse effects were reported. The only discomfort noted was pain during application of the tourniquets. These military studies are similar to what you can expect in this study. Links to the military studies are included on the clinicaltrials.gov web page for this study. This study can be found by searching for “02592655” on the clinicaltrials.gov website, with address <https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT02592655?term=02592655&rank=1>.

What if I am Injured?

If you are injured as a result of your participation in this research project, your insurance company will be billed for the costs of treatment. If you have health insurance, your insurance carrier will be billed in the ordinary manner. As with any health insurance, any costs that are not covered or are in excess of what is paid by your insurance, including deductibles, will be your responsibility. Neither Mercy Health, nor the investigators, nor the FDA, nor the government has any program that would pay the costs associated with a study related injury. No funds have been set aside to pay you in the event of a study related injury. Emergency treatment will be provided if needed; however you or your insurance may be billed for the cost of treatment.

Are there any additional costs to me?

You will not be compensated for expenses associated with your travel to and from the study site in Youngstown Ohio.

What are the possible benefits?

You will not benefit from your participation in this research study. However the knowledge we may gain from your participation may help others. You may chose not to participate at all. If you decide to participate, you can change your mind at any time and it will not adversely affect your relationship with health care providers. If this study discovers important information about your health then you will be informed and an explanation of this finding will be provided to you and the physician of your choice.

How is my privacy protected?

This study does not require access to your health records. All information for this study will be collected directly from you. This form does not authorize another facility to release your health information to this study.

Study records that identify you will be kept confidential as required by law. Study records that identify you will be kept for no less than 7 years by Marcus Migura at (619) 436-7323, Migura@cryptoheaven.com.

Records in this study that that have a letter identifier in place of your name are de-identified. De-identified records will not be held as confidential, and may be released for publication, shared with other researchers or made open to the public on the internet. Your name will not be included in this release. There is a complete example of what these de-identified documents look like at the end of this document. The record that matches your name to the letter identifier will be held as confidential for no less than 7 years by Marcus Migura.

Federal Privacy Regulations provide safeguards for privacy, security, and authorized access. Except when required by law, you will not be identified by name, social security number, address, telephone number, or any other personal identifier in study records disclosed outside of the study staff. The study staff, the reviewing Institutional Review Board (IRB), the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and other government agencies may access your medical records as needed, electronically, by mail, fax or in person.

Who is conducting this research?

This study is being conducted by Marcus Migura and Dr. Joseph Ambrose. Marcus Migura, is responsible for designing, planning, conducting, monitoring, managing and reporting of the study.

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Who is funding this research?

All investigators are donating their time and ability. Mercy Health has provided funding that will be applied to equipment rental, hourly wages for non-investigator technical support and \$25 in compensation for each enrolled volunteer. Your participation in this research study is voluntary. You may withdraw from the study at any time. Volunteers who show up for the study will receive the \$25 check even if they change their mind and decide to withdraw before completing any of the interventions.

Is anyone else supporting or assisting this research?

The investigational tourniquets used in the study have been provided by the manufacturer, Entrotech, at no cost. Entrotech has had no other involvement with the study. Entrotech has no financial relationship with Marcus Migura or Dr. Ambrose.

Tactical Medical Solutions, the manufacturer of the SOFTT-W, has provided enough tourniquets for use in the study, at no cost. Tactical medical solutions has had no other involvement with the study. Tactical Medical Solutions has no financial relationship with Marcus Migura or Dr. Ambrose.

This study has accepted additional support, from Diplomatic Protection Training Institute (DPTI). DPTI provides continuing professional education credits from the National Association of Emergency Medical Technicians (NAEMT) and Ohio Peace Officers Training Academy (OPOTA). DPTI also offers training for the public. DPTI has provided coupons for \$50 off NAEMT, OPOTA or other training provided by DPTI. One coupon is to be given to each volunteer. Volunteers who show up for the study will receive the coupon even if they change their mind and decide to withdraw before completing any of the interventions. You can visit the website, www.DPTI-OH.com to see a complete course list.

This study has accepted assistance from Edwin Lard, the owner of DPTI in the form of donated services. He will train study investigators to use the tourniquets in accordance with the current nationally accepted NAEMT guidelines. Edwin Lard is not an investigator or member of the study staff, he has no financial relationship with Marcus Migura or Dr. Joseph Ambrose.

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Review of the foregoing information:

- You are being asked to participate in a single site and single visit research study involving twenty five healthy individuals. This research will test the ability of experimental and current tourniquets to stop blood flow on your thigh.
- This research has both known and unknown risks described in the preceding pages. **Pregnant women may not participate in this research study.**
- Your participation in this research study is voluntary. You may withdraw at any time without penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled. If your continued participation could expose you or another person to unacceptable risk then your participation may be terminated without your consent. If you withdraw or are removed from the study then you will still receive a \$25 check and \$50 DPTI coupon as described on the earlier pages.
- If you withdraw from the study, no new data about you will be collected for study purposes unless the data concerns an adverse event related to the study. If you decide to withdraw you will be told if there is new information that may influence your decision.
- If you decide to withdraw, or would like to ask more questions you may contact Marcus Migura at (619) 436-7323, Migura@Cryptoheaven.com.
- In the event of research related injury you should contact Dr. Joseph Ambrose at (330) 707-0771, Jambrose52@gmail.com. If you are injured while participating in this study, you will be responsible for the cost of your medical care. No funds have been set aside to pay you in the event of a study related injury.
- If you have any questions regarding your rights as a research subject, you may ask the Chairperson of the Mercy Health Youngstown IRB, Dr. Timothy Barreiro at (330) 480-3610.
- **Notification of Clinical Trial Information Submission for Inclusion in the Clinical Trial Registry Databank:** A description of this clinical trial will be available on <http://www.ClinicalTrials.gov>, as required by U.S. Law. This website will not include information that can identify you. At most, the website will include a summary of the results. You can search this Web site at any time.
- This study is listed on clinicaltrials.gov. You can find the study by searching for the National Clinical Trials number (NCT) which is NCT02592655. The url for this study is <https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/NCT02592655?term=02592655&rank=1>.

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Volunteer's Information**Signature****Printed name****Date signed****Email**

By signing I intend to certify that I have read the foregoing information in this consent form or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and my questions have been answered to my satisfaction. I agree that all risks to me have been explained to my satisfaction. I understand that no compensation is available from the investigators or Mercy Health Youngstown for any injury resulting from my participation in this research. I consent voluntarily to participate as a participant in this research.

Interviewer Information**Signature****Printed name****Date signed****Email**

**NOT VALID WITHOUT THE IRB STAMPED
CERTIFICATION**

**Original IC approved by
Mercy Health Youngstown, LLC IRB
ON: 10/21/2015**

**IRB Approval #: 15-031
Renewed on:
Void After: 10/21/16**